

A statistical and machine learning methodology to model rural depopulation risk and explore its attenuation through agricultural land use management

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ABSTRACT

The abandonment of rural areas has become a major demographical challenge in recent years, especially in Spain and, more specifically, in the Valencian Community. A classification released by the government of this region revealed that almost a third of its municipalities are at depopulation risk. This classification is based on demographic variables, which are valid for identifying the phenomenon but insufficient to provide insight into how to counteract it. Instead, this study developed a methodology to model rural depopulation risk from land use and socioeconomic variables. Correlation analysis and principal component analysis enabled identifying which variables were meaningful for rural depopulation. Then, support vector classification was used to fit the demography-based depopulation classification used by the regional government. The mean accuracy reached was above 80%, which validated the proposed model and variables. Since crop areas was found to be one of the most influential variables in such model, the potential of agro-economic measures to counter depopulation was examined. The results achieved suggested that depopulation might be reduced by 25% if exploiting 25% of the areas suitable for agriculture. In view of these outputs, public administrations may promote the implementation of land use spatial strategies based on sustainable agriculture.

1. Introduction

Rural depopulation has become a recognized fact internationally and a global issue as the degree of urbanisation and industrialisation has increased over the years (Y. Liu & Li, 2017). This has led to an intensification of the social and economic differences between rural and urban areas, thus motivating the outmigration from rural areas to ensure living standards (Y. Li et al., 2019; Sikorski et al., 2020).

The outmigration from rural areas results in a snowball effect whereby the facilities and services required by urban dwellers are progressively reduced (Christiaanse, 2020). The abandonment of rural communities is especially acute in the case of young adults (Amcoff & Westholm, 2007), which couples with the aging of the residents who remain in the area to result in decreased self-autonomy (Lange et al., 2018).

Rural-urban migration has been found to affect both developed and developing areas, including European countries, the United States, China, Australia or Sub-Saharan Africa (Brueckner & Lall, 2015; Markey et al., 2008; Selod & Shilpi, 2021; Terluin, 2003). A particularly

vulnerable country to this phenomenon is Spain, which has the largest number of depopulated areas in Southern Europe (Lorent-Bedmar et al., 2021). The demographic problems of rural areas in Spain persist since the 1960s (Cabre i Cabre Pla & Perez Diaz, 1995) and have increased since the end of the 20th century to the present day.

According to the Spanish Statistical Office (INE, 2021), 25% of the Spanish population lived in towns with less than 2000 inhabitants in 1900. By 1981, this percentage dropped to 9%. In the last 50 years, Spanish rural population has decreased by 28%. This rural exodus can be framed within a process of economic transformation (Hoggart & Paniagua, 2001). Since the World War II, the economic role played by the rural environment all over Europe has become less and less significant because of farmland abandonment, which reduced the importance of agriculture as an employment sector (Garca-Ruiz et al., 2020; Robinson & Sutherland, 2002).

Employment in agriculture has dropped radically in Spain over the last 25 years. In 1976, 22% of the employed population worked in agriculture; however, in 2019, this figure was less than 4% due to changes in agricultural technology, agricultural market globalization

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and lack of infrastructure and services (Garrido & Chuliá, 2020). Spain's decentralised territorial model has not contributed to reverting this situation; in fact, population has continued to concentrate in the centre of the country and in Mediterranean areas (Rubiera Morollón et al., 2016).

Nonetheless, specific strategies to attract population to other intermediate zones through economic activation have not been developed yet. In the end, this territorial imbalance entails demographic risks whose magnitude increase proportionally to rurality (WHO, 2010, p. 40). Under these circumstances, this situation must be understood as a structural problem by public administrations at all levels.

Not in vain, population inequalities among different areas are an economic problem for public accounts, because they make the provision of services and the maintenance of infrastructure more expensive (Camarero & Oliva, 2019). Moreover, this waste of resources hinders the generation of wealth for the country. In this sense, investing in territorial cohesion is necessary and should be deemed as a right in terms of equal opportunities for the different territories and the citizens who live in them.

The socioeconomic and environmental implications of depopulation have boosted the development of research studies in this field, especially during the past two decades (Rodríguez-Soler et al., 2020). For instance, Collantes et al. (2014) conducted a descriptive analysis to examine the impact of immigration on the evolution of Spanish rural population. They found that immigration contributed significantly to reducing depopulation in rural areas.

Without leaving descriptive research, Viñas (2019) investigated the dynamics of rural population decline in Cantabria (Spain). In this case, the author conducted the analysis from different angles based on demographic, geographic and economic indicators, with a focus on the role played by agricultural decline. This conclusion coincides with that achieved by Johnson and Lichter (2019), who linked rural depopulation in the United States to the drop of small farms in favour of increased mechanization and consolidation.

The Valencian Community (eastern Spain) has been the target of other investigations (Alamá-Sabater et al., 2019, 2021), which developed more complex approaches based on fuzzy logic and qualitative comparative analysis, as well as growth and spatial models, to explore depopulation. These authors pointed out to accessibility, economic conditions, population ageing, naturalness and urbanization as the main causes behind population changes, recommending the implementation of plans to both foster local economies and strengthen the links among rural and urban areas.

Other authors have taken approaches to analyse the problem from an environmental perspective. This is the case of (Szymanowski & Latocha, 2021), who built spatial regression models to estimate depopulation in Kłodzko (Poland) from a set of orographic and weather variables. Altitude was also the focus of Castillo-Rivero et al. (2021), since this was an especially atypical factor in their study area (Mexico). Both studies coincided in the difficulties to decoupling environmental or static conditions from dynamic socioeconomic and land use variables.

Overall, previous studies were found to be mainly exploratory and focused on examining the influence of different variables on rural depopulation separately. In most cases, the use of demographic indicators was one of the main benchmarks to evaluate this phenomenon (Paniagua, 2008). In response to this trend, we resorted to a series of land use and socioeconomic variables to model rural depopulation risk.

The few studies that did develop prediction models by combining other types of variables reached limited accuracy, reporting 50% explanatory power at best. They used different forms of regression (spatial autoregression, ordinary least squares regression, geographically weighted regression and mixed geographically weighted regression), which were used to analyse the effect of a limited list of variables on rural depopulation, without conducting any process for variable selection. To achieve more accurate outcomes in the estimation of rural depopulation, we considered a higher number of variables that were

then progressively reduced using a feature selection approach. This is in line with the recommendations commonly found in the literature regarding the importance of variable selection to obtain fitted models capable of predicting new unseen data accurately (Sanchez-Pinto et al., 2018; Speiser et al., 2019).

Hence, the aim of this investigation was to develop a statistical and machine learning methodology to estimate depopulation risk from a series of land use and socioeconomic variables. The proposed approach was applied to the case study of the Valencian Community (eastern Spain), which has been proved to be of special interest in terms of depopulation (Alamá-Sabater et al., 2021). In line with the findings of previous studies (Bruno et al., 2021; Viñas, 2019), the analysis of results was conducted by paying special attention to the role played by agricultural land use.

2. Methodology

Fig. 1 summarises the approach taken to model rural depopulation risk. Using a 4-level demography-based rural depopulation risk classification as a benchmark (0), the mechanism of the proposed methodology aimed at matching such classification by processing a list of socioeconomic and land use variables (1). This started by using correlation and principal component analysis to reduce the initial list of candidate variables according to two criteria: lack of relationship to the risk classification used as a benchmark (1a) and limited explanatory power compared with other candidate variables (1b). Then, support vector machines were used to fit the demography-based classification from the shortlisted variables (1c). Finally, the potential of agricultural land to help counteract rural depopulation is explored through geoprocessing tools (2).

2.1. Case study

The Valencian Community, located in the east of the Iberian Peninsula (Fig. 2), has an area of 23,262 km² (Generalitat Valenciana, 2021c). As such, it is a large region compared with the rest of Autonomous Communities in Spain. Administratively, the region is divided into three provinces: Alicante, Castellón and Valencia (Fig. 2), where the Autonomous Government and the regional capital are located.

Its 518 km of coastline represent more than 20% of the Spanish Mediterranean coast (IGN, 2020). Overall, the climate conditions involve warm and dry winters and hot summers, although there are differences between some areas and others, to the extent that the Köppen classification identifies four types of climate for this region (Chazarra et al., 2011, p. 80). The high average number of days of sunshine per year (300) has fostered an important tourist infrastructure that attracts visitors during all the year (Olcina Cantos & Miró Pérez, 2017, pp. 27–44).

The Valencian Community is one of the Spanish regions with higher economic activity. In terms of macroeconomic data, its Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2020 was 104,724 M€. This represents 9.7% of the total production in Spain and places the Valencian Community as the 4th economy in the country. Its GDP per capita amounted to 20,792 € in 2020 according to the Spanish Statistical Office (INE, 2021).

This region is also the 4th largest Autonomous Community in Spain in terms of population, with 5,058,138 people in 2021. This figure represents an increase of 758 inhabitants with respect to the previous year (Argos, 2021). The share of population per genre is very balanced, with a slight majority of females, who represent 50.74% of the total. The average population density is 217 inhabitants/km², which is clearly above the national average of 95 inhabitants/km² (The World Bank, 2021).

In this sense, there are remarkable demographic imbalances across the region, since most of this population is in the coastal strip due to the progressive displacement of inhabitants from the interior to the coast. As a result, coastal municipalities account for 53% of the population

Fig. 1. Scheme of the steps forming the proposed methodology to model rural depopulation risk.

Fig. 2. Geographical situation of the provinces (Castellón, Valencia and Alicante) in the Valencian Community and depopulation risk classification of its municipalities.

(Generalitat Valenciana, 2021b). This contrasts with inland areas, which are more rural, mountainous, have more extreme climate conditions and lower population density. This circumstance motivated the release of a depopulation risk classification by the regional government. This

initiative showed that 31.5% of the municipalities (171 out of 542) in the region are at different levels of depopulation risk, as indicated in Fig. 2. The variables used to create this classification were demographic, including population density, demographic growth, population growth

rate, aging rate, dependency rate and migration rate.

The severity of the situation has also led to the creation of the so-called AVANT plan 20–30 (AVANT, 2021), a strategic initiative to fight depopulation in the Valencian Community. Based on a diagnosis according to economic, environmental, social, cultural and political dimensions, this plan suggests a set of main actions to revitalise depopulated areas through digitalisation, specialised human resources, housing promotion and economic diversification and strengthening.

To contribute to deploying this plan, depopulation risk was analysed here from a list of socioeconomic and land use variables from the Valencian Territorial Database (Generalitat Valenciana, 2021a). These variables differ from those considered in the risk classification currently used by the Valencian government and in previous research works, which mostly relied on demographic, climate and/or topographic variables (Alamá-Sabater et al., 2021; Castillo-Rivero et al., 2021; Szymanski & Kryza, 2012). Although these can have great explanatory power, their potential to be studied in terms of countermeasures against depopulation is limited.

Table 1 defines the proposed variables, which were originally recorded either as indices, units (persons, buildings, etc.) or areas. Depending on their source format, they were used straightforwardly or expressed as ratios of their values to the population or area in the municipalities, as appropriate. The variables correspond to 2019, since this was the most recent year in which all the required datasets were available. In addition, this year coincides with that in which the Valencian’s depopulation risk classification (Fig. 2) was released (CES-CV, 2020, p. 154).

The first three socioeconomic variables relate to tourism activities, among which accommodation availability and restaurant trade have been found to be important factors in keeping local residents (Cáceres-Feria et al., 2021). Regarding the presence of educational centres, the closure of schools can be a driver for population decline (Lehtonen, 2021). Furthermore, it can foster the disappearance of other institutions such as cultural facilities or libraries (Daugirdas & Pociute-Sereikiene, 2019). The vehicle fleet of a place can also be important for the development of rural areas. On one hand, having public means of transportation such as buses can foster connectedness among villages, towns and cities (Lozano Murciego et al., 2020; Šťastná & Vaishar, 2017). On the other hand, the association between agricultural land abandonment and rural depopulation is influenced by the

Table 1
List of socioeconomic and land use variables proposed to model rural depopulation risk.

Group	Variable	
Socioeconomics	Number of accommodation beds	
	Number of restaurant seats	
	Number of tourism companies	
	Number of educational centres	
	Number of library hubs	
	Number of buses	
	Number of tractors	
	Number of contracts	
	Number of unemployed job-seekers	
	Active population renewal index	
	Land use	Built plots (area)
		Number of commercial properties
		Crop areas
Number of cultural properties		
Number of healthcare properties		
Number of industrial properties		
Number of leisure and hospitality properties		
Non-built plots (area)		
Number of office properties		
Number of residential properties		
Number of sport properties		
Number of urbanisation works		
Vacant land (area)		

relationship between cultivable plots and tractor accessibility (Lasanta et al., 2017). The last three socioeconomic indicators deal with the creation of job positions and the presence of labour for economic productivity. In this sense, higher unemployment rates have been typically argued to have a negative impact on population growth (Goetz & Debertin, 1996; Pires de Almeida, 2017).

Regarding the land use variables, a number of them deal with the basic notion of the degree of development and rapid urbanization (built plots, non-built plots, urbanisation works and vacant land) as drivers of depopulation (P. Liu et al., 2020). Some others focus on aspects that might help face depopulation by improving the quality of life of inhabitants through cultural and healthcare services and sports facilities (Merino & Prats, 2020). House availability has also been mentioned as a moderately important factor for depopulation; however, its relevance depends on the number of new offers, the condition of available houses or their prices (Rodríguez-Rodríguez & Larrubia Vargas, 2022). The remaining variables (commercial properties, crop areas, industrial properties, leisure properties and office properties) deal with economic development, whose changes have been emphasised as a main cause for rural depopulation over many years (Bayona-i-Carrasco & Gil-Alonso, 2013; X. Li, 2015; Saville, 2013).

2.2. Correlation analysis

The correlation between the variables in Table 1 and depopulation risk was explored using the Kendall’s tau coefficient (Kendall, 1938), a non-parametric test used to measure the monotonic association between two variables. This fits the ordinal nature of the response variable, which includes 4 levels of depopulation risk (Fig. 2). A pair of municipalities could be concordant, discordant or tied depending on whether they corresponded to the same level of risk with respect to two variables or not. Based on this, Kendall’s tau (τ) is mathematically defined as formulated in Eq. (1).

$$\tau = \frac{c - d}{c + d} \tag{1}$$

where c refers to the number of concordant pairs and d stands for the number of discordant pairs. In case of ties (t), half of them is considered concordant and half discordant, such that $\tau = (c - d)/(c + d + t)$. Kendall’s tau was preferred over the Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient because it has been argued to be less sensitive to outliers, more effective for small sample sizes and more tractable in mathematical terms, especially if there are ties (Gilpin, 1993).

The values of Kendall’s tau between depopulation risk in the municipalities of the Valencian Community and the variables in Table 1 were determined using R’s cor.test function (R Core Team, 2020). A level of significance of 0.05 (Fisher, 1992) was set to identify which variables were statistically related to depopulation risk. Therefore, those variables whose τ was associated with a p-value below 0.05 were discarded for further analyses.

This process was a first screening to eliminate variables that were not significantly correlated to depopulation risk. A second step consisted of building a correlation matrix storing the values of τ among all the variables in Table 1. The aim here was to identify which variables were highly correlated to others, because they would not be providing new information to model depopulation risk. Moderate-to-strong correlations for Kendall’s tau have been associated with values of 0.5 or -0.5 (McCarty et al., 2021). These values were taken as a cut-off to determine if any variable was highly correlated to others using the findCorrelation function in R’s caret package (Kuhn et al., 2021). Hence, if two variables were highly correlated to each other ($\tau \geq 0.5$ or $\tau \leq -0.5$), the one showing the highest mean value of τ with respect to all the remaining variables was removed from next steps.

2.3. Principal component analysis

Due to the high number of variables initially considered (Table 1), those remaining after correlation analysis were still expected to be even more reducible. To this end, they were further processed using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) (Pearson, 1901). This technique converts a set of possibly correlated variables into a subset of more tractable and linearly uncorrelated principal components through an orthogonal transformation (Jolliffe & Cadima, 2016).

These components are determined by projecting the data in multiple directions that maximize their variance. Hence, the first principal component corresponds to the linear combination of variables that maximizes the most variance, whereas subsequent components maximize variance among all directions orthogonal to the previously computed directions (Hotelling, 1933). Mathematically, a principal component z_j can be defined as expressed in Eq. (2).

$$z_j = X^* v_j \quad (2)$$

where X is an input matrix of m rows and n columns representing the municipalities and variables in the dataset, respectively, and v_i are the principal component directions or eigenvectors obtained through a singular value decomposition of X (Wall et al., 2003). Since PCA is based on variance maximization, the data in X must be standardized to avoid any dominance by those variables involving larger ranges.

PCA was run using the built-in R function `prcomp`. This yielded the cumulative proportion of variance explained by each component (from 0 to 1), as well as their corresponding eigenvectors. Each eigenvector is formed of a set of values commonly referred to as loadings, which represent how much each variable contributes to the principal components. These loadings were used to reduce the number of variables according to a series of criteria as listed below.

- Keep the number of components corresponding to a cumulative proportion of variance of 0.90, since this threshold was expected to capture most of the information in the data.
- Find the greatest contributors to the shortlisted components by determining which variables have an absolute loading equal to or greater than the ninth decile of each component.
- Perform a sum of the absolute loadings of the most contributing variables across the shortlisted components.
- Weight the summed values according to the cumulative proportion of each component to gain insight into the overall importance of the variables.
- Remove those variables whose weighted sum is zero, because they were assumed to be uninfluential for modelling depopulation risk.

2.4. Support vector classification

Support Vector Classification (SVC) applies supervised learning models known as support vector machines to solve classification problems. It consists of finding the hyperplane that best differentiates a set of classified observations (Cortes & Vapnik, 1995). In the context of this study, SVC was used to classify the municipalities of the Valencian Community according to their level of depopulation risk using the variables shortlisted in previous steps.

The goodness of classification was measured through the concept of margin, which represents the width of the band around the hyperplane for a given weight vector w and bias b (Fig. 3). Hence, the target is to find the optimal hyperplane for which d maximizes the separation among classes. This is equivalent to minimizing $\|w\|$ with the condition that there are no interior data points within the band.

Fig. 3 illustrates the simplest case of two classes. For multiclass problems with k classes like this study, SVC can be implemented using a 'one-against-one' approach where $k*(k-1)/2$ binary classifiers are trained. In this case, this meant that the original 4-level classification

Fig. 3. Graphical representation of support vector classification with linearly separable data. The yellow band represents the margin that separates two classes (green circular points and red squared points).

dataset was split into one dataset for each class versus every remaining class, which eventually resulted in six classifiers.

SVC works better if the number of samples is similar for all classes, because otherwise the model might be biased. In view of Fig. 2, this imbalance exists in the case study due to a higher number of municipalities at low risk of depopulation. To deal with this situation, the training dataset was balanced before proceeding with classification. This was carried out using the `upSample` function in the `caret` package (Kuhn et al., 2021), which enabled sampling with replacement to match the size of all classes.

Then, the classification model was built using R's `svm` function in the `e1071` package (Meyer et al., 2021), which implements different kernel functions to build classification models. The cost and gamma parameters in SVC were set with the support of the `tune` function. As in the PCA, the variables used for classification were standardized, since the minimization of $\|w\|$ is influenced by the scale of the inputs.

The weight of the variables used as predictors was computed using the `Importance` function in R's `rminer` package (Cortez, 2020). It is based on a sensitivity analysis that measures changes in the response when the inputs are varied through their ranges of values (Cortez & Embrechts, 2013). Since the explanatory variables were shortlisted in previous steps, variance in the response was determined through 1D sensitivity analysis (no interactions among the predictors).

2.5. Measures to counter rural depopulation

Based on the classification model above described, next was exploring potential measures to fight rural depopulation risk. Given the acknowledged role of agricultural activity to fight depopulation (EESC, 2021), these measures were conceived under the assumption that crop areas played an important role in modelling depopulation risk. As such, they were designed based on the exploitation of suitable areas for crop yield. This course of action is aligned with the third target (2.3) of the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 2, which seeks to double the agricultural productivity and incomes of small-scale food producers (UN, 2015).

The identification of suitable areas for crop yield was carried out through the geoprocessing of land cover and lithological maps. These were acquired from the Corine Land Cover (CLC) project (European Union, 2015) and the Geological and Mining Institute of Spain (IGME, 2017) at 1:100,000 and 1:200,000 scales, respectively. Potentially arable land without requiring earthmoving preparation tasks was associated with vegetated and open spaces corresponding to the following CLC classes: 3.2 (shrub and/or herbaceous vegetation associations), 3.3.3 (sparsely vegetated areas) and 3.3.4 (burnt areas).

The appropriacy of soils for crop yield is subject to several restrictions, since most of them are too wet, too dry, too shallow or chemically inadequate (FAO, 2021). With these limitations in mind, loamy soils and other mixtures of sand, silt and/or clay were deemed

suitable for agricultural productivity due to their balance in terms tillage, nutrients, water retention and warming (Brady, 1984).

Once valid arable land classes and adequate soils were identified, both inputs were intersected to identify suitable areas for crop yield. The agricultural areas already in operation, which correspond to the CLC class 2, were subtracted from the original set of suitable areas to keep only those that provided added value. Then, three different strategies to attenuate rural depopulation with increasing degrees of exploitation of these areas were simulated: 10%, 25% and 50%.

These ratios aim at resembling different scenarios whereby public administrations may promote the search for new areas conducive to crop yield for increasing agricultural productivity. The choice of these three specific figures (10%, 25% and 50%) was set with the sole purpose of illustrating the increasing effect of the strategies as the area affected increases. In this sense, 50% stands for a very optimistic and unlikely upper bound, whereas 10% corresponds to a lower bound in which the effects of the attenuation measures can start to be noticeable.

There have been recent initiatives in Spain aligned with this course of action. For instance, Castilla y Leon's Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Rural Development approved in March 2022 a project to expand the areas devoted to horticultural crops in the region (ITACyL, 2022). Also, the Agrarian Association of Young Farmers has requested the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture to increase the crop area for sunflower, whose availability is being endangered by the Russia-Ukraine conflict (Virtudes, 2022). In the end, this kind of actions seek to promote economic development and sustainability through local and civic agriculture (Delind & Bingen, 2008).

In terms of calculation, the impact of these strategies was expressed at the municipality scale, in line with the format of the variables in Table 1. Hence, the variable accounting for crop areas was increased by adding the percentage of new arable land in each municipality to the original crop areas. In addition, there were other variables having agro-economic implications: contracts, unemployed job-seekers and tractors. The number of tractors required to work crop areas was recalculated proportionally to the increase in crop areas for the three scenarios considered. Contracts and unemployed job-seekers were updated according to the Agricultural census in Spain (Eurostat, 2020). These data include the number of persons working on farms and total utilised agricultural area for the Valencian Community in 2000 and 2010. This information provides the ratio of workers per crop area, thereby enabling the recalculation of both variables considering the increased values of crop areas.

3. Results

3.1. Correlation analysis

The correlation between the initial set of 23 candidate explanatory variables (Table 1) and depopulation risk was measured through Eq. (1). Two variables were found to be statistically insignificant: healthcare property and non-built plots. The former suggested that depopulation was not favoured by the distribution of medical facilities, whilst the lack of significance of the latter might lie in the ambiguity of the term, since it encompasses both buildable and non-buildable areas.

The strength of the values of Kendall's tau for the remaining variables is depicted in Fig. 4. Public services such as schools, buses and libraries, as well as the occupation of the inhabitants, either directly (contracts and unemployment) or indirectly (shops and office), were found to be inversely related to depopulation. Instead, aspects concerning accommodation, leisure and restaurants were proportional to the level of depopulation risk. This suggests that strategies to fight against depopulation shall rely on business activity unrelated to the hospitality industry, which is a cornerstone in the Spanish economic model (Hidalgo & Maene, 2017). The negative values of Kendall's tau obtained for the agriculture-related variables point out to their promotion as a path to deal with depopulation. In contrast, the industry sector

and variables related to the ratio of development in the municipalities impacted positively on depopulation risk.

The variables listed in Table 1 were further processed through an internal correlation analysis. This process revealed that residential property was highly correlated to vacant land (Kendall's tau = 0.52), which in turn was highly correlated to industrial property (Kendall's tau = 0.55). The mean correlation for the first pair of variables was 0.295 (residential property) and 0.138 (vacant land). Therefore, residential property was dropped henceforth for having stronger correlations with the remaining variables. The subsequent results for vacant land and industrial property corresponded to values of mean correlation of 0.213 and 0.122, respectively. Following the same logic, vacant land was removed from the set of variables considered for next steps.

The positive association between residential property and vacant land might relate to a process of sprawl whereby people may move to peripheral areas within the municipalities due to housing prices, a car-oriented culture or a search for quietness (Sperandelli et al., 2013). In turn, this may lead to decreased infrastructure provision and land use in some areas (Kim, 2016). Also, job loss derived from the closure of plants and manufacturing hubs has also been identified as a potential cause for increased vacant land (Garvin et al., 2013).

3.2. Principal component analysis

As a result of the correlation analysis, the number of candidate variables to perform as predictors of depopulation risk was reduced from 23 to 19. These 19 variables were used as inputs to carry out a PCA, whose loadings per principal component are shown in Fig. 5. The values in the abscissa axis revealed a progressive gain in cumulative variance, highlighting the difficulties to reduce the dimensionality of the variables used as potential predictors because of their distinctiveness.

PC1 was rather balanced, with two property-related variables of different nature (industry and leisure and hospitality) showing the highest loadings. PC2 showed more cohesion, with a dominance by the service sector through the combination of shops and offices with accommodation and restaurants. The remaining components highlighted the preponderance of some variables such as tractors (PC3 and PC11), buses (PC4 and PC8), tourism companies (PC5), contracts (PC6), educational centres (PC4 and PC7) or crop areas (PC8 and PC15).

To shed light on the results in Fig. 5, only the first fifteen components were considered due to their correspondence to most of the cumulative variance (0.90). Following the remaining criteria set in the methodology, those variables having absolute loadings equal to or greater than the ninth decile across the fifteen components were aggregated to obtain a weighted value representing their relevance. These results indicated that the weighted value of restaurant seats and sport property was zero.

Fig. 4. Strength and direction of the correlations between the significant explanatory variables and depopulation risk in the Valencian Community.

Fig. 5. Loadings of the explanatory variables across the principal components in which data was reduced. High absolute loadings indicate that variables have strong influences on the components.

In other words, none of them was among the most important variables (ninth decile) with respect to any of the fifteen components with the greatest variance, probably because of their overlap with other variables such as leisure and hospitality property. The removal of these two variables reduced the final number of predictors for classification to 17: 9 socioeconomic and 8 land use variables.

3.3. Support vector classification

The first step to build the SVC model was to split the 542 municipalities of the Valencian Community into training and testing observations according to a 70:30 ratio (Nguyen et al., 2021). Two thirds of the municipalities (262) in the former corresponded to a low level of depopulation risk. As such, the training dataset was upsampled to balance the number of observations, so that there were 262 observations per level of risk.

The testing of kernel functions revealed that the linear one reached low accuracy when modelling the training subset. Instead, a tuned radial kernel function (gamma = 0.1 and cost = 1) yielded a value of Kendall's tau of 0.88 and a mean classification accuracy of 89.5%. The confusion matrix in Fig. 6a shows the breakdown of this value across the four levels of risk. The ability of the classifier to distinguish among groups was ratified by the values of Area Under the Curve (AUC) in Fig. 6c, which were almost 1 for all four classes.

The testing dataset contained 109, 13, 12 and 17 municipalities with low, moderate, high and very high risk, respectively, which means an even higher imbalance than in the training subset. This led to a reduced accuracy in the confusion matrix and AUC plots in Fig. 6. Still, the values of Kendall's tau (0.66) and mean accuracy (77.5%) were high because the model was very precise in distinguishing between absence (low) and presence (moderate, high and very high) of depopulation risk. In what concerns presence of risk, the highest number of true positives corresponded to very high (Fig. 6b), which highlights the capacity of the classifier for identifying extreme depopulation risk. The values of AUC in Fig. 6d were between 0.6 and 1, ranging from acceptable to high chances of distinguishing among classes (Howe et al., 2014; Qiu et al., 2020). The greatest difficulties were found in the differentiation between

moderate and high risk, whose AUC was barely above 0.5.

The results of the sensitivity analysis conducted to determine the importance of the variables in the SVC model are shown in Fig. 7, which revealed a rather balanced distribution of weights. The five most important explanatory variables represented very different aspects related to business activity, job, public services in the form of education and transportation and agriculture. This balance ensures that the model built accounts for a variety of aspects whose management can have an important impact on rural depopulation.

The degree of agreement between these weights and both the values of Kendall's tau in Fig. 4 and the PCA loadings in Fig. 5 was only partial, since the purposes of these methods differ from each other. Still, the ratio of crop areas per municipality was the variable showing higher values across all three analyses. It corresponded to the fourth most important predictor in terms of classification, the second largest negative correlation to depopulation and one of the combinations of higher loadings across more components (PC1, PC6, PC8, PC14 and PC15).

3.4. Measures to counter rural depopulation

The high influence of crop areas supported the analysis of attenuation measures based on agricultural activity. Given the higher vulnerability of Castellón (Fig. 2) to depopulation risk, the analysis was narrowed to this province. The geoprocessing and combination of land cover and lithological maps revealed that the magnitude of suitable areas for crop yield in Castellón amounted to 1219.55 km² (Fig. 8). Hence, the three strategies posed to counteract depopulation risk with increasing degrees of exploitation of these areas (10%, 25% and 50%) resulted in 122 km², 305 km² and 610 km².

The effects of the three strategies were expressed in the agriculture-related variables in Table 1: crop areas, contracts, unemployed job-seekers and tractors. The results of these changes are mapped in Fig. 9, which compares the baseline situation with the three alternative scenarios where crop areas increased progressively. Due to the more balanced distribution of depopulation risk levels across Castellón (Fig. 2), the predictions yielded by the SVC model for this province were very precise: 108 out of 135 true positive outcomes for a mean accuracy

Fig. 6. Accuracy of the Support Vector Classifier (SVC) to model the four levels of depopulation risk in the Valencian Community: confusion matrices for the (a) training and (b) testing datasets; Area Under the Curve (AUC) for the (c) training and (d) testing datasets.

Fig. 7. Weights of the explanatory variables involved in the Support Vector Classifier (SVC) to model depopulation risk.

of 80%.

The maps in Fig. 9 suggest that the agro-economic measures proposed might be effective in attenuating depopulation. The number of municipalities whose depopulation risk was reduced because of the use of suitable areas for agricultural productivity was as follows: 6 for 10% (3 from very high to low), 22 for 25% (4 from high and 5 from very high to low) and 28 for 50% (9 from high and 13 from very high to low). These figures indicated that depopulation may be reduced in ~25% of Castellón’s municipalities (22 out of 86) when exploiting the agro-economic potential of 25% of their arable areas.

In general, the trends in Fig. 9b, c and d reveal how the strategies were especially effective in the northwest of Castellón. This confirms the particularly critical situation of the municipalities placed in mountainous areas, whose population may have moved to the coast (east). This is especially remarkable for the capital city of the region, which is located opposite (southeast) these risky municipalities. The number of municipalities affected by the proposed measures increased substantially from 10% (6) to 25% (22) but remained rather constant from there (28 for 50%). In this sense, the intermediate scenario might be considered optimal, since it results in a high number of benefited

Fig. 8. Distribution of suitable areas for agriculture across Castellón's municipalities.

municipalities and only two cases in which the level of risk is high.

As for the 50% scenario, the variations mostly concerned the intensity of the effect, with 12 municipalities decreasing their level of risk from high or moderate to low with respect to the 25% scenario. To delve into this matter, the effect of the strategies was compared using the Fisher exact test, which evaluates whether there is a significant difference between the categories (levels of risk) of two variables (strategies). The p-values returned by the test were above a significance level of 0.05 in all cases (10% vs 25%, 10% vs 50% and 25% vs 50%), which means that the levels of risk associated with the three scenarios were not significantly related to each other. In other words, the effect of the proposed measures was different and incremental in terms of intensity.

In any case, these results should be taken with caution, since they refer to a simulation of hypothetical scenarios based on the association between crop areas and depopulation, whose causality is rather indirect. Although their impact cannot be verified directly in terms of accuracy, they are built upon the reliability of the classification model previously developed and validated in Fig. 6, and the rationale and importance (Figs. 4, Figs. 5 and 7) behind the variables affected by these scenarios. Therefore, the simulated scenarios at least provide insight into the potential of exploiting crop areas for the purpose of dealing with rural depopulation.

4. Discussion

The results achieved confirmed the validity of the approach taken to fill the research gaps identified in previous literature. On one hand, the proposed methodology served to model rural depopulation risk from the combined analysis of a series of explanatory variables. This differs from the general focus of past works, which explored depopulation trends from separate standpoints such as migration, aging, public services or elevation. On the other hand, the accuracy in Fig. 6 goes beyond that of the few works that built estimation models. Alamá-Sabater et al. (2021) reported values of R^2 of 0.39 for estimating population growth, whereas the model developed by Szymanowski and Latocha (2021) was capable of explaining 54% of depopulation variance.

The data used to analyse depopulation are the other main difference

with respect to past investigations. In this sense, the present study was limited compared with others based on topographic and/or climate factors (Castillo-Rivero et al., 2021; Szymanowski & Latocha, 2021), which are accessible worldwide. However, this kind of variables stand for physical and atmospheric features on which it is difficult to take actions to deal with depopulation. Instead, the variables depicted in Fig. 7 have clearer policy implications. Governments and administrations can foster the implementation of measures to stimulate aspects such as job creation, agricultural productivity, tourism reactivation and educational and/or health centre creation.

Furthermore, despite the data used here stemmed from a regional source, the list of variables proposed in Table 1 can also be found in other local repositories or in global open data portals. For instance, the OpenStreetMap initiative (OSM, 2008) provides data on the same variables in some cases (e.g., 'schools' and 'libraries' in the amenity category or 'industrial' and 'sports' in the building category) or on others that can be used as proxies for them (e.g., bus stops/routes or hotels as indicators of the number of buses and accommodation beds). Similarly, gridded data available at the Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center (SEDAC, 2011) can be used as indicators of economic variables. This is the case of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), which keeps an inversely proportional relationship with unemployment rate according to Okun's law (Hjazeen et al., 2021). Regarding crop areas, they can be determined from land cover maps such as the Corine Land Cover (CLC) (European Union, 2015).

Other authors have previously stressed the potential of agriculture to counter depopulation in Mediterranean regions thanks to its ecosystem services (Bruno et al., 2021). Furthermore, these same authors also reported a negative association between crops and depopulation, as suggested by Fig. 4.

Regarding the exploitation of these crop areas, they have been projected to be especially sensitive to frequent and severe water shortages induced by climate change (Tsanis et al., 2011). This fact would hinder intensive agriculture (Iglesias et al., 2011) due to their higher requirements in terms of acquisition and maintenance of machinery. The role of agriculture for maintaining population size in Spanish communities was predominant in the past; however, agricultural modernisation based on labour-saving innovations (Pinilla & Sáez, 2021) and subsequent economic crises led to a progressive exodus to other regions more developed in industrial terms (Cáceres-Feria et al., 2021). The correlation of crop areas and industrial property with depopulation risk (Fig. 4) may suggest that climate alterations might be causing a shift in this trend, whereby self-production for local consumption of food could be gaining interest, especially because of its potential for reducing carbon footprint (Puigdueta et al., 2021).

Therefore, agro-economic strategies to reverse depopulation as the one proposed in this study should rely as much as possible on extensive practices based on locally available resources, thereby reducing the use of synthetic inputs such as fertilizers and pesticides (Móznér et al., 2012). This course of action is aligned with the recovery of traditional techniques and consumption of local products advocated by Bruno et al. (2021), which would also result in co-benefits such as water purification or biodiversity enhancement (Lockwood, 1999).

The promotion of extensive farms is important for stimulating agriculture to fight depopulation through the generation of employment, since intensive methods are led by technological innovation that decreases the use of labour (Coomes et al., 2019). There are programs that can support this, like the one launched by the UK Government (Defra, 2022). This initiative offers pilot incubators to support new entrants of any age in the agricultural sector looking to either start-up or scale-up their own land-based business in the first 10 years. Some of these entrants may implement the organic agricultural practices supported by the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) (European Commission, 2021) in their crop areas and thus contribute to local economic activity, since extensive agriculture has been argued to have higher direct income and employment effects than intensive agriculture (Giannakis &

Fig. 9. Reduction in depopulation risk in the province of Castellón with respect to a (a) Baseline scenario: alternative scenarios involving (b) 10% increase in crop areas, (c) 25% increase in crop areas and (d) 50% increase in crop areas.

Efstratoglou, 2011). Furthermore, these agricultural activities should focus on crops rather than on livestock to avoid depopulation and aging (Pôças et al., 2011). Ideally, young people should be particularly targeted for this kind of actions, as underlined by the 6th European Youth Goal ('Moving Rural Youth Forward'). In this vein, the European Network for Rural Development has reported several successful cases of young people developing new agricultural economic activities that create local jobs in rural areas (Giorgi, 2022).

The strategies proposed in Fig. 9 are also on the same page that the conclusions drawn by Rodríguez-Dolton-Thornton (2021) for the same study area, whereby local development and employment were argued to be main aspects to avoid depopulation. In addition, these authors pointed out to the capacity of agriculture for generating the required developments in multiple dimensions. In this vein, other authors like del Río et al. (2021) showed how viticulture might favour demographic settlement in Northwest Spanish rural areas if crops are cultivated in

suitable areas. Although vineyards are not so dominant in the Valencian Community (12% of its arable land) (Generalitat Valenciana, 2021a), this approach might be applied to citrus (29%), whose quality and worldwide reputation is demonstrated by its Protected Geographical Indication (PGI) (IGP Cítricos Valencianos, 2021).

In the end, these actions would contribute to the third target of the second Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) (United Nations, 2022), which seeks to promote sustainable production and consumption by protecting family farming based on extensive and traditional systems. Supporting this type of practices would strengthen the adaptability of agricultural holdings to deal with climate change challenges such as desertification or extreme events, which is related to the fourth target of the second SDG.

The importance of sustainable agriculture has also reached the political sphere. As indicated in the "Action plan for the implementation of the 2030 Agenda" of the Government of Spain, fostering short

distribution channels can significantly help local scale farmers to improve their income level, while bringing consumers closer to sustainable and high-quality production (Gobierno de España, 2018). Also, a recent report by the Spanish Economic and Social Council highlighted the primary role of the agricultural sector to ensure the sustainability of the rural environment and favour job creation in these areas (CES, 2021, p. 234).

5. Conclusions

The results of this study proved the effectiveness of the proposed methodology to model depopulation risk in the Valencian Community (Spain), a region where rural exodus has become a serious issue over the last years. The combination of statistical methods and machine learning algorithms was found to estimate the level of depopulation risk in the municipalities of the study area with high accuracy.

The application of these methods led to discard 6 out of the initial 23 candidate predictors for subsequent steps. These factors were related to healthcare, hospitality and undeveloped land, especially when coupled with residential areas. The removal of the first variable was positive in that it involved that the absence of nearby medical facilities was not a reason favouring depopulation. Otherwise, these results suggested that the fight against depopulation should not go through the hospitality and construction industries, which have traditionally been very important business activities in Spain.

In contrast, both the statistical analyses and the machine learning classification pointed out to the use of crop areas as an effective path to attenuate depopulation. As such, a series of strategies based on land use management for sustainable agriculture were designed. These strategies, which were applied to the province of Castellón due to its particularly high vulnerability, consisted of simulating the effect of exploiting suitable areas for crop yield in terms of soil and land cover on depopulation risk. The results indicated that using 25% of these areas for agriculture may reduce at least one level of risk in 25% of the municipalities where depopulation was an issue.

The characteristics of these agro-economic measures should be in line with current environmental and socioeconomic challenges, which include water scarcity, increased carbon footprint, low quality goods and unemployment. The implementation of extensive and family agricultural practices can help deal with these aspects, thereby contributing to meeting several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In light of this reasoning, public administrations should promote agricultural development through land use planning by incentivizing the adoption of sustainable practices with financial aids, thus limiting the presence of intensive agriculture entailing higher water requirements, less labour per capita and poorer quality production. This course of action would help mitigate some of the effects posed by climate change, while contributing to achieving local sustainability and healthier diets.

Despite the validity of the outcomes reached, the significance of this research is limited by the data used, which stems from a regional repository and only applies the boundaries of the study area. This hinders the direct extrapolation of the inferences derived from this analysis to other regions where rural depopulation is also an important problem. Hence, additional models should be created using global open data to cluster broader regions according to their rural depopulation risk and drivers under different contexts. This would enable tailoring the proposal of attenuation measures to the specifics of the depopulation clusters identified. Furthermore, the impact of these measures should be assessed more in detail by considering aspects such as the effects of labour-saving technologies and the location of the increased crop areas.

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None.

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